

Distribution-Adaptive SNR Filtering for Date Palm Cultivation Imagery

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ABSTRACT. *Field-acquired agricultural images, particularly in arid environments, often suffer from quality degradation caused by intense solar irradiance, airborne dust, canopy occlusion, and variable shadows. These factors introduce intensity variability that can reduce the reliability of downstream machine learning pipelines.*

Existing preprocessing approaches generally follow one of two strategies: image enhancement, which may introduce processing artifacts, or fixed quality thresholds that fail to account for the statistical characteristics of the target dataset.

This paper proposes a distribution-adaptive quality filtering method in which the acceptance threshold is derived directly from the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) distribution of the dataset itself. A per-image SNR proxy is computed, and the rejection threshold is adjusted automatically using the coefficient of variation (CV), allowing the method to apply stricter selection to homogeneous datasets and more permissive selection to heterogeneous ones without manual calibration or external reference.

Evaluated on a field-acquired dataset of 17,976 date palm images spanning 12 classes, the proposed method retains 86.5% of images, increases mean SNR by 9.2%, and reduces within-dataset variance by 17.8%. After five-fold augmentation, the filtered subset preserves its quality advantage over the unfiltered baseline, with a 7.7% increase in mean SNR. A paired bootstrap analysis further indicates that pre-filtering does not alter the distributional response of images to augmentation, supporting the filter-then-augment strategy as both effective and statistically neutral.

Overall, the results show that dataset-driven quality selection can improve training set homogeneity while preserving photometric diversity in field-acquired agricultural imagery.

Keywords: adaptive quality filtering; signal-to-noise ratio; image quality assessment; dataset curation; field-acquired imagery; data augmentation; agricultural image processing; precision agriculture.

1. Introduction. Date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) is the principal crop of arid southern Algeria, with more than 18.6 million palms producing approximately 1,489,830 tonnes annually, placing the country among the three largest date-producing nations worldwide [1, 2]. Production is concentrated in the southeastern provinces, with Biskra contributing 31% of national output, followed by El Oued (27%) and Ouargla (18%) [3]. Because of its economic importance, effective phytosanitary management is essential for maintaining both productivity and crop value. Pests and diseases are estimated to account for 20% to 40% of agricultural losses in affected regions [1]. In Algeria, the main threats to date palm cultivation include the Boufaroua mite (*Oligonychus afrasiaticus*), dubas bug infestations, and fungal diseases such as brown spot and white scale, all of which are further exacerbated by changing climatic conditions [4]. Current monitoring practices still rely largely on manual inspection and subjective evaluation, which often delay detection until visible damage has already progressed. Deep learning and computer vision techniques offer a promising alternative for automated disease monitoring and crop health assessment [5]. Their deployment in date palm cultivation, however, remains technically challenging under real field conditions. Field observations in the Sidi Okba agricultural region of Biskra (34.7506° N, 5.9084° E) highlight the environmental complexity of image acquisition in date palm oasis ecosystems. Fig. 1 provides the spatial context of the acquisition site.

FIGURE 1. Satellite imagery of the Sidi Okba date palm oasis (Biskra, Algeria; 34.7506° N, 5.9084° E), acquired 11 November 2025. Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data 2025, processed by the authors.

Automated image acquisition in date palm oases is affected by several degradations that are difficult to isolate and control, including intense solar illumination that produces specular reflections on waxy frond surfaces, airborne dust that reduces contrast, three-dimensional canopy structures that generate variable shadows, and the naturally high texture variability of healthy foliage. In the dataset used in this study, measured SNR values range from near zero to approximately 21 dB, consistent with the quality conditions reported for unconstrained field agricultural imagery [6]. Acquisition-level degradation of this magnitude can propagate through augmentation and training pipelines, reducing model robustness even when the architecture is well-designed [7]. Existing preprocessing strategies generally follow two directions. Correction-based denoising methods may improve visual appearance, but they can also introduce artifacts that alter the features on which classifiers depend [7, 8]. Fixed-threshold quality filters avoid such transformations, yet they apply uniform criteria without considering the statistical quality distribution of the target dataset. To address these limitations, we propose an adaptive SNR filtering pipeline in which the acceptance threshold is derived from the coefficient of variation of the dataset’s own SNR distribution. The method therefore requires neither an external quality reference nor manual threshold tuning. It is evaluated on a multi-source field-acquired dataset of 17,976 date palm images collected under realistic agricultural conditions, spanning 12 categories that include both healthy references (healthy leaves, healthy dates, and healthy bunches) and nine pathological conditions: brown spot and white scale pathologies [9], dubas bug infected specimens exhibiting honeydew manifestations [10], nutrient deficiencies (potassium, manganese, magnesium), fusarium wilt, leaf spot, rachis blight, and Boufaroua-infested specimens [11], together with exclusive field imagery provided by the Institut National de Protection des Végétaux (INPV), Algiers. All imagery was collected under operational field conditions, without controlled laboratory acquisitions.

Section 2 presents the background on agricultural image quality challenges and the proposed algorithm. Section 3 provides an illustrative numerical example. Section 4 describes the dataset construction and experimental methodology. Section 5 analyzes computational complexity. Section 6 presents the experimental results. Section 7 discusses the implications of the findings and future directions. Section 8 concludes the paper.

2. Background and Proposed Algorithm. Crop diseases remain a major threat to global food security, and their early identification is particularly difficult in date palm

cultivation, where dense canopy structure and harsh desert conditions complicate visual assessment. At the same time, the widespread availability of smartphones and recent advances in deep learning have made automated disease diagnosis increasingly feasible [5]. Computer vision methods for crop disease detection have shown strong performance across multiple crop types [12]. Their effectiveness, however, depends not only on the model architecture but also on the quality of the acquired images. Imaging device characteristics, spatial resolution, and acquisition conditions directly influence segmentation, feature extraction, and classification performance, making image quality a key requirement for reliable downstream analysis [15]. A large-scale review by Song et al. of 2,156 studies published between 2010 and 2025 reported that approximately 43% explicitly addressed environmental challenges in agricultural image processing [6]. This sustained attention reflects the difficulty of working with images acquired outside controlled settings. Under open-field conditions, uneven topography, variable illumination, and changing weather generate disturbances such as weeds, shadows, reflective water surfaces, and occluding branches, all of which can obscure salient crop features and reduce the accuracy of detection, segmentation, and classification tasks. In applications such as pest identification or fruit detection, soil textures and partially occluded plant structures may be mistaken for lesions or target objects, thereby reducing model reliability [6]. For this reason, preprocessing quality deserves careful attention, particularly when the input data exhibit substantial variability. Evidence for this principle exists across pipeline types: quality enhancement of dark images has been shown to substantially improve the reliability of downstream binarization [13], and super-resolution preprocessing of aerial rice imagery has been reported to raise CNN-based disease-classification accuracy from 79.97% to 86.96% [14], confirming that upstream image-quality improvements translate into measurable gains in the final task. Objective image quality assessment is an important component of robust computer vision systems operating under unconstrained conditions [15, 16]. In this work, we use the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) computed from the grayscale representation of each image as the primary quality indicator. For a grayscale image with pixel mean μ and standard deviation σ , SNR is defined as:

$$\text{SNR}_{\text{dB}} = 20 \times \log_{10} \left(\frac{\mu}{\sigma + \varepsilon} \right), \quad \varepsilon = 10^{-6}, \quad (1)$$

where ε ensures numerical stability when $\sigma \approx 0$. In this formulation, the pixel mean μ represents the image signal, while the standard deviation σ captures the combined effect of acquisition noise and intensity variability, following standard practice in image quality assessment [15]. Converting each image to grayscale before computation avoids inter-channel dependency effects and yields a single luminance-based quality estimate [15]. Throughout this paper, the term SNR refers to this luminance-based proxy rather than to a true signal-to-noise ratio requiring a noise-free reference image; it quantifies the ratio of mean intensity to intensity spread and therefore serves as a tractable per-image quality indicator under unconstrained acquisition conditions. This formulation is consistent with the main degradation modes observed in desert agricultural imagery. Haze and dust tend to reduce μ while increasing σ ; sensor overexposure shifts μ toward saturation while compressing σ ; and strong illumination gradients increase σ independently of object content. In each case, the resulting effect is a reduction in SNR according to Eq. (1). A domain-specific factor must also be considered: high-frequency vegetative textures, including leaf venation and surface microstructure, increase σ and therefore produce lower SNR values than those typically observed under controlled imaging conditions. This helps explain why field-acquired date palm images in our setting fall within a 0–21 dB range, substantially below the 20–40 dB range commonly associated with controlled acquisition

environments [16, 15]. Rather than relying on external benchmarks derived from different imaging conditions, the proposed method calibrates its selection criterion relative to the statistical baseline of the dataset itself. Data augmentation introduces another practical complication. When augmentation is applied to already degraded images, geometric transformations, photometric adjustments, and synthetic perturbations can compound existing quality defects rather than simply increase sample diversity [17]. Denoising methods may partially address this issue, but both classical and deep learning-based approaches introduce additional computational cost [7]. Adaptive filtering methods generally perform better than fixed strategies when noise conditions vary across images [8]. However, most of these methods are designed to modify images through denoising, enhancement, or restoration, rather than to select images on the basis of intrinsic quality. Fixed-threshold filtering presents a different limitation. It applies the same quality criterion to all datasets and therefore assumes that noise characteristics and quality distributions remain broadly comparable across acquisition settings. In agricultural imagery, this assumption is often unrealistic because image quality varies with location, season, illumination, sensor type, and field conditions. In practice, many standard thresholds fall in the 15–25 dB range and are inherited from general-purpose photography benchmarks. For agricultural imagery, where SNR values are often systematically lower, such thresholds may discard 60–80% of field-acquired samples, leading to an unacceptable reduction in usable training data. Neither correction-based preprocessing nor fixed-threshold filtering uses the statistical structure of the target dataset to guide quality-based selection. To address this gap, we propose a dataset-driven quality filtering algorithm in which the acceptance threshold is derived from the intrinsic statistical properties of the input SNR distribution. The procedure requires no external quality reference and no manual calibration. **Phase 1: High-quality bypass.** If the minimum SNR across all valid images meets or exceeds an absolute floor $SNR_{\text{abs}} = 30$ dB, all images are retained without filtering. This bypass prevents unnecessary processing when the dataset is already uniformly high in quality; it is not activated for the field dataset used in this study.

Phase 2: Adaptive threshold selection. The acceptance threshold is computed as:

$$\tau = \text{median}(\text{SNR}) - k \cdot \sigma_{\text{SNR}}, \quad (2)$$

where k is an adaptive coefficient scaled by the coefficient of variation of the SNR distribution:

$$CV = \frac{\sigma_{\text{SNR}}}{\mu_{\text{SNR}}}, \quad k = \text{clip}(\alpha \cdot CV, k_{\min}, k_{\max}), \quad (3)$$

with $\alpha = 3.0$, $k_{\min} = 0.5$, $k_{\max} = 2.0$. The median is preferred over the mean in Eq. (2) to ensure robustness against the heavy lower tail typical of field imagery, where a few severely degraded samples can skew distributional statistics. In the present dataset, the near-identical mean and median values (both ≈ 7.23 dB, Sec. 6.1) confirm approximate symmetry, indicating that this choice preserves threshold stability across both symmetric and skewed distributions. These constants were chosen to provide stable behavior across the heterogeneity range commonly observed in field-acquired agricultural datasets. The scaling factor $\alpha = 3.0$ maps typical CV values in the 0.2–0.5 range to a useful operating range for k , spanning moderate to relatively permissive selectivity. The lower bound $k_{\min} = 0.5$ prevents overly aggressive filtering in homogeneous datasets, where excessive rejection could remove still-usable images. The upper bound $k_{\max} = 2.0$ prevents overly permissive behavior in heterogeneous datasets, where severely degraded images might otherwise be retained. The effect of these parameters on retention rate and quality improvement is examined in Section 3. When dataset heterogeneity is high (large CV), k increases and τ decreases, making the selection rule more permissive. This reduces the

risk of over-rejecting a dataset whose broad spread reflects genuine acquisition variability rather than uniformly poor quality. When heterogeneity is low (small CV), k moves toward k_{\min} and τ rises toward the median, leading to stricter selection. In this way, the procedure adapts automatically to the statistical profile of each dataset without requiring manual threshold adjustment. The complete procedure is formalized in Algorithm 1. The algorithm takes as input a set of images and returns the filtered subset after computing one scalar quality proxy per image. Lines 1-2 compute the per-image SNR and retain finite values; lines 3-5 handle the degenerate case in which no finite SNR exists; line 6 extracts the summary statistics μ_{SNR} , z , and σ_{SNR} ; lines 7-9 implement the Phase 1 bypass for uniformly high-quality datasets; and lines 10-12 perform the adaptive threshold computation and image selection of Phase 2.

Algorithm 1 Adaptive SNR Filtering Algorithm

Require: Images $I = \{I_1, \dots, I_N\}$; $SNR_{\text{abs}} = 30$ dB; $\alpha = 3.0$; $k_{\min} = 0.5$; $k_{\max} = 2.0$; $\varepsilon = 10^{-6}$

Ensure: Filtered subset $I_{\text{filtered}} \subseteq I$

- 1: Compute per-image SNR: $SNR_i = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\mu_i}{\sigma_i + \varepsilon} \right) \forall I_i \in I$
 - 2: Retain finite values: $SNR^{(v)} = \{SNR_i \mid SNR_i \text{ is finite}\}$
 - 3: **if** $SNR^{(v)} = \emptyset$ **then**
 - 4: **Abort:** all SNR values non-finite
 - 5: **end if**
 - 6: Compute: $\mu_{\text{SNR}} = \text{mean}(SNR^{(v)})$, $z = \text{median}(SNR^{(v)})$, $\sigma_{\text{SNR}} = \text{std}(SNR^{(v)})$
 - 7: **if** $\min(SNR^{(v)}) \geq SNR_{\text{abs}}$ **then**
 - 8: **return** $I_{\text{filtered}} = I$ (*Phase 1*)
 - 9: **end if**
 - 10: Compute: $CV = \sigma_{\text{SNR}} / \max(|\mu_{\text{SNR}}|, 10^{-6})$, $k = \text{clip}(\alpha \cdot CV, k_{\min}, k_{\max})$
 - 11: Compute threshold: $\tau = z - k \cdot \sigma_{\text{SNR}}$
 - 12:
 - 13: **return** $I_{\text{filtered}} = \{I_i \in I \mid SNR_i \geq \tau\}$
-

The decision logic of Algorithm 1 is illustrated in Fig. 2. The flowchart highlights the two-stage structure of the method: the lateral branch corresponds to the Phase 1 bypass for uniformly high-quality datasets, whereas the downward branch corresponds to Phase 2, in which CV , k , and τ are derived sequentially from the statistics of the dataset.

FIGURE 2. Flowchart of the adaptive SNR filtering algorithm.

Rather than attempting to restore degraded acquisitions, the proposed pipeline selects images according to their position within the dataset's own quality distribution. The aim is to improve dataset homogeneity while preserving the distributional characteristics of the retained images for subsequent augmentation. This property is evaluated empirically in Section 6. This selective-retention strategy is consistent with current data-centric AI practice, in which systematic data quality engineering can be as important as model design for downstream performance [18].

3. Illustrative Example. To illustrate the behavior of the proposed algorithm, we apply it to a set of $N = 20$ manually constructed SNR values spanning the range [1.9, 8.2] dB, using the same parameter values as in the full experiment: $\alpha = 3.0$, $k_{\min} = 0.5$, $k_{\max} = 2.0$, and $SNR_{\text{abs}} = 30$ dB.

Input SNR values (dB):

{1.9, 2.1, 2.3, 2.8, 3.1, 3.5, 3.8, 4.1, 4.3, 4.5, 4.5, 4.9, 5.2, 5.5, 5.9, 6.2, 6.6, 7.0, 7.6, 8.2}

Algorithm trace:

1. *Statistics.* All 20 values are finite. The corresponding summary statistics are

$$\mu_{\text{SNR}} = \text{mean}(\text{SNR}^{(v)}) = 4.70 \text{ dB}, \quad z = \text{median}(\text{SNR}^{(v)}) = 4.50 \text{ dB},$$

$$\sigma_{\text{SNR}} = 1.8 \text{ dB}, \quad \text{SNR}_{\text{min}} = 1.9 \text{ dB}.$$

2. *Phase 1 check.* Because $\text{SNR}_{\text{min}} = 1.9 \text{ dB} \ll \text{SNR}_{\text{abs}} = 30 \text{ dB}$, the high-quality bypass is not activated, and the procedure continues to Phase 2.

3. *Adaptive coefficient.*

$$CV = \frac{\sigma_{\text{SNR}}}{\mu_{\text{SNR}}} = \frac{1.8}{4.70} = 0.38, \quad k = \text{clip}(3.0 \times 0.38, 0.5, 2.0) = 1.15.$$

4. *Adaptive threshold.*

$$\tau = z - k \cdot \sigma_{\text{SNR}} = 4.50 - 1.15 \times 1.8 = 2.43 \text{ dB}.$$

5. *Selection.* Images with SNR values in {1.9, 2.1, 2.3} dB fall below τ and are therefore rejected.

$$|I_{\text{filtered}}| = 17, \quad \text{retention rate} = 85\%.$$

3.1. Sensitivity to Dataset Heterogeneity. Table 1 shows how the adaptive coefficient k and the corresponding threshold τ vary with distributional spread while keeping the median fixed at $z = 4.50 \text{ dB}$ and the mean at $\mu_{\text{SNR}} = 4.70 \text{ dB}$. The example illustrates the main adaptive behavior of the method: selection becomes stricter for more homogeneous distributions and more permissive for more heterogeneous ones.

TABLE 1. Adaptive threshold behavior across four heterogeneity scenarios.

Scenario	σ_{SNR}	CV	$\alpha \cdot CV$	k	τ (dB)	Behavior
Low heterogeneity	0.6	0.13	0.38	0.50*	4.20	Strict
Moderate	1.2	0.26	0.77	0.77	3.58	Balanced
Present example	1.8	0.38	1.15	1.15	2.43	Moderate
High heterogeneity	2.4	0.51	1.53	1.53	0.83	Permissive

*Clipped to $k_{\text{min}} = 0.5$ since $\alpha \cdot CV = 0.38 < k_{\text{min}}$.

Two observations are useful here. First, the threshold always remains below the distribution median, which ensures majority retention across all four scenarios. Second, the clipping bounds k_{min} and k_{max} prevent extreme behavior: $k_{\text{min}} = 0.5$ avoids overly aggressive filtering in highly homogeneous datasets, whereas $k_{\text{max}} = 2.0$ prevents the threshold from becoming excessively permissive in highly heterogeneous ones.

3.2. Comparison with Fixed Thresholds. To place the adaptive threshold in context, Table 2 compares it with two fixed-threshold strategies applied to the same 20-value sample.

TABLE 2. Threshold strategy comparison on the $N = 20$ illustrative example.

Strategy	τ (dB)	Rejected	Retained
Fixed high	5.0	12/20 (60%)	8/20 (40%)
Fixed low	2.0	1/20 (5%)	19/20 (95%)
Adaptive (proposed)	2.43	3/20 (15%)	17/20 (85%)

The fixed high threshold rejects 60% of the sample, even though the distribution does not suggest that most images are unsuitable for training. The fixed low threshold retains almost all images, including those that lie well below the dataset baseline. By contrast, the adaptive threshold removes only the lower tail of the distribution while preserving most of the sample.

This example is intended only to clarify the mechanics of the algorithm on a small and transparent input. Experimental results on the full field-acquired dataset ($N = 17,976$ images) are presented in Section 6.

3.3. Sensitivity to the Scaling Factor α . The scaling factor α controls how strongly the coefficient of variation influences the adaptive coefficient k . Table 3 examines its effect on threshold placement and retention rate using the same 20-value illustrative sample, with all other parameters held fixed ($z = 4.50$ dB, $\sigma_{\text{SNR}} = 1.8$ dB, $CV = 0.38$).

TABLE 3. Effect of α on adaptive threshold and retention rate ($z = 4.50$ dB, $\sigma_{\text{SNR}} = 1.8$ dB, $CV = 0.38$; $N = 20$).

α	$\alpha \cdot CV$	k	τ (dB)	Retained
1.5	0.57	0.57	3.47	15/20 (75%)
2.0	0.76	0.76	3.13	16/20 (80%)
3.0	1.14	1.14	2.43	17/20 (85%)
4.0	1.52	1.52	1.76	20/20 (100%)
5.0	1.90	1.90	1.08	20/20 (100%)

Two observations follow from Table 3. First, the retention rate is relatively stable in the range $\alpha \in [2.0, 3.0]$, varying by only five percentage points (80% to 85%), which suggests that the method is not highly sensitive to moderate changes in α around the reference value. Second, for $\alpha \geq 4.0$, the threshold falls below the minimum observed SNR value and all images are retained, making the filter ineffective. The value $\alpha = 3.0$ was therefore selected as it places the threshold at the lower tail of the distribution without approaching the floor of the observed range, and without rejecting an excessive proportion of usable images. Sensitivity on the full field-acquired dataset follows the same monotonic pattern, since $CV = 37.3\%$ is close to the illustrative value of $CV = 0.38$.

4. Methodology and Experimental Setup.

4.1. Dataset Construction. The dataset was assembled from approximately 23,607 candidate date palm images drawn from six sources: a date palm leaf disease collection covering eight disease categories captured from ten date farms in the Madinah region, Saudi Arabia [19]; an intelligent harvesting collection [9]; a dubas bug infection dataset [10]; a Boufaroua field survey dataset [4]; a Boufaroua image collection [11]; and field imagery provided by the Institut National de Protection des Végétaux (INPV), Algiers. From this initial pool, controlled laboratory acquisitions captured under artificial lighting were removed, near-duplicate images within the same capture session were excluded using a structural similarity index measure (SSIM) threshold greater than 0.95, and corrupt or unreadable files were discarded. The final dataset comprises 17,976 images spanning 12 categories.

4.2. Experimental Configurations. Four experimental configurations were defined to isolate the effects of quality filtering and augmentation order:

- **Raw (R):** the unfiltered dataset.
- **Filtered (F):** images retained by the adaptive SNR filter (Algorithm 1).
- **Raw Augmented (R-Aug):** R expanded by a factor of five through augmentation.
- **Filtered Augmented (F-Aug):** F expanded by a factor of five through augmentation.

The comparison between F and R isolates the effect of quality filtering alone. The comparison between F-Aug and R-Aug then tests whether the effect of filtering persists after augmentation, thereby providing empirical support for the filter-then-augment ordering.

4.3. Data Augmentation Protocol. SNR-based filtering was applied to the original-resolution images before any resizing. Images were then resized to 224×224 pixels, consistent with standard CNN input dimensions, and subsequently expanded into five augmented variants through randomly sampled transformations [17]. The complete pipeline therefore follows the order: quality filtering on full-resolution images, resizing, and augmentation. Three families of transformations were applied. Geometric transformations included random rotation ($\pm 30^\circ$), horizontal and vertical flipping, and random cropping with aspect-ratio preservation. Photometric perturbations covered brightness adjustment ($\pm 20\%$), contrast modification, and gamma correction ($\gamma \in [0.8, 1.2]$). Synthetic degradations were limited to additive Gaussian noise ($\sigma_n \in [0.01, 0.03]$) and mild Gaussian blur ($\sigma_b \in [0, 1.0]$). For each source image, five independent random draws from this transformation space produced five distinct variants, ensuring that no two augmented copies of the same image were identical.

4.4. Evaluation Metrics. Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). The per-image SNR defined in Eq. (1) serves as the primary quality indicator. For each configuration, we report the mean SNR ($\overline{\text{SNR}}$), standard deviation (σ_{SNR}), median, and interquartile range (IQR). A lower σ_{SNR} indicates a more homogeneous training set [5].

Sobel Gradient Energy (SGE). SGE measures the average squared gradient magnitude and is defined as [20]:

$$\text{SGE}(I) = \frac{1}{H \cdot W} \sum_{x,y} [G_x(x,y)^2 + G_y(x,y)^2], \quad (4)$$

where G_x and G_y denote the horizontal and vertical Sobel filter responses, and $H \times W$ denotes the image dimensions. SGE is evaluated alongside SNR to examine whether gradient-based structural measures respond to augmentation differently from intensity-based quality measures. It is used only as a characterization metric for the pipeline and not as a decision variable for filtering.

Diversity Score (D). The diversity score quantifies photometric variability as the mean pairwise L2-normalized RGB histogram distance:

$$D = \frac{2}{N_s(N_s - 1)} \sum_{i < j} \left\| \hat{h}_i - \hat{h}_j \right\|_2, \quad (5)$$

computed over a subsample of $N_s = 1,000$ images, where \hat{h}_i is the L2-normalized 768-dimensional RGB histogram vector (256 bins per channel). L2-normalization ensures that $D \in [0, 2]$. Because augmentation generates five derived variants around each source image, it compresses histogram distances within local clusters. For this reason, the relevant diversity comparison for assessing the effect of filtering is between R-Aug and F-Aug rather than between augmented and unaugmented configurations. The computation is repeated over five deterministic seeds (0–4), and the reported value is the mean \bar{D} with standard deviation σ_D .

Bootstrap Paired Analysis. A paired bootstrap analysis [21] is used to test whether SNR-based pre-filtering alters the structural response of images to augmentation. Let $\mathcal{B} = \{I_1, \dots, I_n\}$, with $n = 200$, denote the set of base images present in both the R-Aug and F-Aug branches. For each base image I_i , the augmentation protocol generates five stochastic variants in each branch (see Section 4); the corresponding *per-image mean* Sobel gradient energy is defined as

$$\overline{\text{SGE}}_i^{(\cdot)} = \frac{1}{5} \sum_{j=1}^5 \text{SGE}(I_{i,j}^{(\cdot)}), \quad (\cdot) \in \{\text{R-Aug}, \text{F-Aug}\}, \quad (6)$$

so that intra-variant stochasticity is averaged out before pairing. The paired structural difference for image I_i is then

$$\Delta_i^{\text{SGE}} = \overline{\text{SGE}}_i^{(\text{F-Aug})} - \overline{\text{SGE}}_i^{(\text{R-Aug})}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad (7)$$

yielding a single paired sample of size $n = 200$, which matches the values visualized in Fig. 8. Because both branches undergo the same family of augmentation transformations, any augmentation-induced inflation of gradient energy cancels in the paired difference, isolating the effect attributable to pre-filtering.

Bootstrap 95% confidence intervals for $\mathbb{E}[\Delta^{\text{SGE}}]$, $\text{median}(\Delta^{\text{SGE}})$, and $P(\Delta^{\text{SGE}} > 0)$ are estimated from $B = 3,000$ resamples of $\{\Delta_i^{\text{SGE}}\}_{i=1}^n$ drawn with replacement, using the [2.5th, 97.5th] percentile method without imposing a parametric distributional assumption [21]. Structural neutrality of the filter is supported when (i) the confidence interval for the mean paired difference contains zero, and (ii) $P(\Delta^{\text{SGE}} > 0) \approx 0.50$, indicating that filtered and unfiltered branches exhibit statistically indistinguishable responses to augmentation.

4.5. Method Comparison. Table 4 summarizes the main properties of the proposed algorithm relative to existing alternatives.

Fixed-threshold filtering ignores the statistical distribution of image quality within a given dataset. Correction-based approaches, by contrast, introduce additional computational cost and carry a risk of processing artifacts [7, 8]. The proposed method differs in that it combines distribution-aware selectivity with the absence of manual threshold tuning, external quality references, and image-level correction.

4.6. Implementation. All experiments were conducted in MATLAB R2024b on a workstation equipped with an NVIDIA RTX 2060 SUPER GPU and 16 GB RAM. Per-image SNR was computed by converting each RGB image to grayscale using the luminance formula [15] and then applying Eq. (1). SGE was computed using 3×3 Sobel operators

TABLE 4. Comparison of image selection and filtering strategies for field-acquired agricultural datasets.

Property	No filter	Fixed threshold	Correction	Proposed
External reference	No	No	No	No
Manual tuning	N/A	Yes	Partial	No
Adapts to distribution	N/A	No	No	Yes
Computationally efficient	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Artifact risk	None	None	Yes	None
Handles heterogeneous SNR	N/A	No	Partial	Yes
Class-neutral selection	N/A	No guarantee	No guarantee	By design*

*Per-class retention varies with acquisition conditions (Section 6), not class identity.

according to Eq. (4) [20]. Diversity histograms used 256 bins per RGB channel as defined in Eq. (5). The bootstrap procedure used $B = 3,000$ resamples with $n = 200$ paired differences [21]. All experiments were run with deterministic random seeds to ensure reproducibility of the reported measurements.

5. Computational Complexity Analysis. Computing the SNR for a single image requires one linear pass over all pixel values in order to estimate the grayscale mean μ_i and standard deviation σ_i . For a dataset of N images, each containing $M = H \times W$ pixels, the total cost of per-image SNR computation is

$$\mathcal{O}(N \cdot M). \quad (8)$$

The subsequent thresholding step operates on N scalar SNR values. Computing the standard deviation and coefficient of variation is linear in N , while computing the median requires sorting and therefore adds $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$. For realistic image sizes, where $M \gg \log N$, this additional cost is negligible relative to the per-image SNR computation. The overall complexity of the filtering pipeline therefore remains $\mathcal{O}(N \cdot M)$.

Table 5 compares this complexity with that of standard preprocessing approaches. Unlike correction-based methods, the proposed algorithm operates at the image level by computing a single scalar quality indicator for each image and then applying a binary accept/reject rule. As a result, it avoids the per-pixel neighborhood operations that dominate the computational cost of denoising and restoration methods.

TABLE 5. Computational complexity of image quality management methods.

Method	Objective	Complexity	Notes
Proposed adaptive SNR	Image selection	$\mathcal{O}(N \cdot M)$	No neighborhood operations
Gaussian filter (separable)	Noise reduction	$\mathcal{O}(N \cdot k \cdot M)$	Separable; $\approx 3\times$ for $k=3$
Median filter	Impulse noise removal	$\mathcal{O}(N \cdot k^2 \cdot M \log k)$	Per-pixel sorting
Bilateral filter	Edge-preserving smoothing	$\mathcal{O}(N \cdot k^2 \cdot M)$	Non-separable
FFDNet [8]	CNN denoising	$\mathcal{O}(N \cdot M \cdot L)$	GPU required

Note: N denotes the number of images, M the number of pixels per image, k the kernel size, and L the network depth.

Correction-based methods introduce a per-pixel neighborhood cost that scales with the kernel size k , ranging from $\mathcal{O}(N \cdot k \cdot M)$ for separable Gaussian filtering to $\mathcal{O}(N \cdot M \cdot L)$ for deep denoising networks such as FFDNet [8]. For small kernels ($k = 3$), this overhead remains moderate, but it becomes substantially larger for wider kernels or multi-layer network architectures. By contrast, the proposed method computes a single scalar statistic

per image and applies one threshold comparison, which eliminates neighborhood-based processing entirely.

On the experimental dataset ($N = 17,976$ images of size 224×224), the MATLAB implementation processes the full filtering pipeline in approximately 31 seconds, corresponding to about 580 images/s. This runtime indicates that the method is practical for large-scale automated preprocessing in precision agriculture settings.

The auxiliary evaluation metrics exhibit compatible scaling. SNR and SGE both require $\mathcal{O}(N \cdot M)$ computation, the diversity score requires $\mathcal{O}(N_s^2)$ per seed independently of N , and the bootstrap analysis requires $\mathcal{O}(B \cdot n)$, which is a fixed overhead for the chosen values of B and n .

6. Experimental Results.

6.1. Filtering Effect on the Raw Dataset. On the raw dataset of $N = 17,976$ images, the algorithm yields $\text{median}(\text{SNR}) = 7.23$ dB, $\sigma_{\text{SNR}} = 2.69$ dB, and $CV = 37.3\%$, which correspond to an adaptive coefficient $k = 1.12$ and a threshold $\tau = 4.22$ dB at the 14.9th percentile of the SNR distribution. Fig. 3 places this threshold within the full dataset distribution. Most values are concentrated between 5 and 12 dB, with a declining lower tail below 4 dB. The threshold lies at the left shoulder of the distribution, rejecting 2,423 images and retaining $N_f = 15,553$ images (86.5%).

FIGURE 3. Per-image SNR distribution of the raw dataset.

The near-identical mean and median values (both 7.23 dB) reflect the approximate symmetry of the raw SNR distribution, as visible in Fig. 3.

The effect of filtering on the distributional statistics is shown in Fig. 5 and summarized in Table 6. Two changes are immediately apparent:

- Mean SNR increases from 7.23 to 7.90 dB (+0.67 dB, +9.2%), indicating higher average image quality in the retained subset.
- Standard deviation decreases from 2.69 to 2.21 dB (−17.8%), indicating greater within-dataset homogeneity.

TABLE 6. Quality metrics across the four pipeline configurations.

Config.	N	Mean SNR (dB)	σ_{SNR} (dB)	Median (dB)	ΔMean	$\Delta\sigma_{\text{SNR}}$	SGE	D
Raw	17,976	7.23	2.69	7.23	—	—	0.1007	0.843
Filtered	15,553	7.90	2.21	7.73	+9.2%	−17.8%	0.0966	0.809
Raw Aug.	89,880	5.47	2.00	5.49	—	—	0.2264	0.757
Filt. Aug.	77,765	5.89	1.71	5.78	+7.7%	−14.5%	0.2142	0.749

Note: ΔMean and $\Delta\sigma_{\text{SNR}}$ are computed relative to Raw for Filtered and relative to Raw Aug. for Filt. Aug. D is mean photometric diversity over $N_s = 1,000$ images (five seeds).

The lower whisker of the Filtered distribution rises to approximately +4 dB, whereas the Raw distribution extends below 0 dB, indicating the emergence of a quality floor after filtering.

(A) SNR = 8.57 dB (retained).

(B) SNR = 11.01 dB (retained).

FIGURE 4. Representative images retained by the adaptive filter.

Fig. 4 Shows that the retained examples preserve visible frond microstructure, lesion boundaries, and chromatic contrast between healthy and affected tissue, confirming compatibility with downstream classification.

FIGURE 5. SNR distributions across the four pipeline configurations.

The narrower interquartile range and raised lower bound of the Filtered distribution are visually apparent. The next subsection examines whether these gains remain after augmentation.

6.2. Per-Class Retention and Imbalance Analysis. Because the adaptive threshold τ (Eq. 2) is applied uniformly to SNR values without reference to class labels, the filter is class-neutral by design. Any per-class retention variability therefore reflects acquisition heterogeneity (illumination, sensor type, source collection) rather than pathological identity. Table 7 reports the image distribution across the 12 categories before and after filtering, together with the resulting per-class retention rates.

TABLE 7. Per-class image distribution before and after adaptive SNR filtering.

ID	Category	Before	After	Retention (%)
C1	Healthy Leaves	3,708	3,448	93.0
C2	Healthy Dates	1,163	1,122	96.4
C3	Healthy Bunches (Leaves + Dates)	3,130	2,613	83.5
C4	Brown Spot	1,638	1,241	75.8
C5	White Scale	1,054	1,010	95.8
C6	Dubas Bug	1,749	1,494	85.4
C7	Honeydew	902	776	86.0
C8	Nutrient Deficiency (K / Mn / Mg)	1,038	968	93.2
C9	Fusarium Wilt	914	742	81.2
C10	Leaf Spot	1,248	726	58.2
C11	Rachis Blight	809	799	98.8
C12	Boufaroua	623	614	98.6
Total		17,976	15,553	86.5

Class imbalance, measured as the ratio between the largest and smallest category, slightly decreases after filtering: $IR_{\text{before}} = 3,708/623 \approx 5.95$ versus $IR_{\text{after}} = 3,448/614 \approx 5.62$ ($\Delta IR \approx -0.33$, a -5.5% relative change). The reduction is marginal and arises because the most abundant category (Healthy Leaves) loses proportionally more samples than the smallest ones (Boufaroua, Rachis Blight). This confirms that SNR-based filtering does not introduce additional class imbalance; on the contrary, it mildly attenuates it. The only category experiencing substantial loss is Leaf Spot (-41.8%), whose retained 726 samples remain sufficient for downstream training while targeted augmentation can compensate for the reduced count. Automated per-class retention monitoring is nevertheless recommended as a complementary practice to identify acquisition-driven retention gaps in future deployments, as outlined in the Future Work section.

6.3. Preservation of Quality Advantage Through Augmentation. After five-fold augmentation, the quality advantage established by filtering remains visible. As reported in Table 6, the Filtered Augmented configuration outperforms Raw Augmented on both quality indicators, with mean SNR values of 5.89 versus 5.47 dB ($+7.7\%$) and σ_{SNR} values of 1.71 versus 2.00 dB (-14.5%).

Fig. 6 provides a visual comparison across the four configurations. Among them, Filtered Augmented yields the lowest σ_{SNR} value (1.71 dB), lower than Raw (2.69), Filtered (2.21), and Raw Augmented (2.00), making it the most homogeneous training set produced by the pipeline.

As expected, augmentation lowers absolute SNR values because of added noise and photometric perturbation. However, the gap between the filtered and unfiltered branches is maintained. This result supports the use of the filter-then-augment order within the proposed pipeline.

FIGURE 6. Summary metrics across the four pipeline configurations.

6.4. Quality-Diversity Analysis. Fig. 7 shows the quality diversity operating points for the four configurations. As explained in Section 4.4, the relevant diversity comparison is between the two augmented configurations, because augmentation compresses intra-cluster histogram distances regardless of prior filtering. Under this comparison, Filtered Augmented yields $D = 0.749$ whereas Raw Augmented yields $D = 0.757$, corresponding to a difference of $\Delta D = 0.008$, which is less than one percentage point on a $[0, 2]$ scale. This difference is stable across all five subsampling seeds. The unaugmented configurations show a larger gap: Raw ($D = 0.843$) versus Filtered ($D = 0.809$), corresponding to $\Delta D = 0.034$. This wider separation is expected, since filtering removes 2,423 lower-quality images from the source pool. After augmentation, which is the operationally relevant scenario for training dataset construction, the gap narrows to $\Delta D = 0.008$. This indicates that the effect of filtering on photometric diversity is negligible in the augmented regime.

FIGURE 7. Quality-diversity operating points for the four configurations.

Filtering therefore improves SNR homogeneity at a diversity cost of $\Delta D = 0.008$ in the augmented regime, a difference of less than 0.5% on the $[0, 2]$ scale. The next analysis evaluates whether filtering also preserves the structural response of images to augmentation.

6.5. Bootstrap Validation of Structural Neutrality. The paired bootstrap analysis evaluates whether pre-filtering changes the structural response of images to augmentation. Two paired comparisons are considered: (1) the filtering effect (Filt. Aug. minus Raw Aug., same images), and (2) the augmentation effect (Augmented minus Raw, same images).

6.5.1. Filtering Effect: Structural Neutrality. Fig. 8 shows the per-image mean SGE in the Filtered Augmented branch versus the Raw Augmented branch for $n = 200$ matched base images. The distribution is nearly symmetric around the $y = x$ identity line, with 101 points above (50.5%) and 99 below (49.5%). The branch-level mean SGE values are both 0.2160.

The bootstrap distribution of the mean paired difference (Fig. 9, left panel) yields:

- Mean $\overline{\Delta SGE} = -6.4 \times 10^{-5}$
- 95% CI: $[-0.0077, +0.0076]$ (contains zero)
- $P(\Delta > 0) = 0.505$, with 95% CI $[0.436, 0.574]$ (contains 0.50)

These results indicate that pre-filtering does not measurably alter the structural gradient-energy response of images after augmentation.

FIGURE 8. Paired mean SGE values for Filtered Augmented and Raw Augmented images.

The scatter pattern provides a visual complement to the bootstrap analysis and is consistent with structural neutrality.

6.5.2. *Augmentation Effect: Structural Inflation.* Applying the same bootstrap procedure to the augmentation effect (Fig. 9, right panel) yields a markedly different result:

- Mean $\overline{\Delta SGE} = +0.130$
- 95% CI: [+0.112, +0.148] (entirely above zero)
- $P(\Delta > 0) = 0.825$, with 95% CI [0.772, 0.878] (entirely above 0.50)

These values show that augmentation systematically increases SGE for most images. The contrast between the two analyses is informative. The same statistical procedure that clearly detects the augmentation effect finds no comparable effect of filtering. This asymmetry supports the interpretation that structural neutrality is a genuine property of the filtering stage rather than a consequence of insufficient statistical sensitivity.

FIGURE 9. Bootstrap distributions of paired Δ ^{SGE}.

6.6. SNR and SGE Behavior Under Augmentation. Table 6 shows that SNR and SGE respond in opposite directions to augmentation. When augmentation is applied to the raw dataset:

- SGE increases by +124.8% (from 0.1007 to 0.2264).
- SNR decreases by -24.3% (from 7.23 to 5.47 dB).

These opposite trends reflect different sensitivities to the augmentation operations. Geometric transformations such as rotation, cropping, and flipping, together with synthetic degradations such as noise injection and blur, introduce high-frequency content at

boundaries and within altered regions. This tends to increase Sobel gradient responses, thereby inflating SGE, while also increasing pixel-intensity variability relative to the mean, thereby reducing SNR.

The right panel of Fig. 7 illustrates this separation clearly. Pre-augmentation configurations cluster around $\text{SGE} \approx 0.10$, whereas post-augmentation configurations cluster around $\text{SGE} \approx 0.22$. This shift is driven by augmentation; filtering itself produces only negligible SGE change within each group.

This divergence matters for the choice of filtering proxy. A selection rule based on SGE would assign higher quality scores to augmented images than to their unaugmented source images, which is opposite to the intended ranking. By contrast, SNR decreases after augmentation and therefore preserves the expected ordering in which source images are rated higher than their augmented derivatives. Table 8 summarizes this contrast.

TABLE 8. Response of SNR and SGE to augmentation.

Metric	Raw	Raw Aug.	Change
Mean SNR (dB)	7.23	5.47	-24.3%
Mean SGE	0.1007	0.2264	+124.8%

These results support the use of SNR as the quality proxy for filtering in augmentation-aware pipelines, whereas a gradient-based alternative such as SGE would reverse the desired ordering between original and augmented images.

7. Discussion. The proposed adaptive SNR filtering algorithm improves mean SNR by 9.2% and reduces distributional variance by 17.8% while retaining 86.5% of the original images. These results suggest that the method can improve dataset homogeneity without imposing a large loss of training volume. In this section, we discuss the implications of these findings, their practical relevance for agricultural computer vision, and several directions for future work.

7.1. Interpretation of the Filtering Outcome. The adaptive threshold $\tau = 4.22$ dB corresponds to the 14.9th percentile of the raw SNR distribution, which means that the algorithm removes only the lower tail while retaining most of the central mass and upper range. This behavior follows directly from the CV-driven calibration. With $CV = 37.3\%$, the dataset exhibits moderate heterogeneity, and the resulting operating point ($k = 1.12$) yields a threshold that improves average quality without causing excessive rejection. Two aspects of this outcome are worth emphasizing. First, the increase in mean SNR (+9.2%) and the decrease in standard deviation (-17.8%) are consistent with the selective removal of lower-quality samples from a broadly unimodal distribution. What distinguishes the proposed method from a fixed-threshold strategy is that the threshold is not imposed externally. Instead, it is derived from the statistical structure of the dataset itself. In this sense, the algorithm identifies a data-dependent transition between the low-quality tail and the main body of the distribution without requiring manual inspection. The 17.8% reduction in σ_{SNR} Table 6 provides a direct, distribution-level quantification of improved dataset homogeneity. Prior work in data-centric AI has established that reduced training-set variance correlates with improved optimization stability and generalization [18], supporting the claim that homogeneity gains benefit downstream pipelines even in the absence of end-to-end classification results. Second, the retention rate of 86.5% represents a reasonable compromise between quality improvement and data preservation for the present dataset. Out of 17,976 images, 2,423 are discarded. Because the level of selectivity depends on the shape of the SNR distribution, the method becomes more

permissive for highly heterogeneous datasets and more selective for more homogeneous ones. This adaptive behavior helps limit both excessive rejection and insufficient filtering. Because the threshold is applied to SNR values rather than class labels, variation in per-class retention is driven by acquisition conditions rather than by an explicit class-dependent rule. In that sense, the filtering process is class-neutral at the algorithmic level. Classes acquired under more difficult field conditions may still show lower mean SNR and therefore higher rejection rates, but this reflects differences in image quality rather than preferential treatment of one pathological category over another. An additional practical advantage is that per-class retention remains measurable, which can support targeted supplementary data collection when needed. The per-class distribution reported in Table 7 is consistent with this behavior: retention rates vary between 58.2% and 98.8% across the 12 categories, while the imbalance ratio between the largest and smallest class remains essentially stable (5.95 before versus 5.62 after filtering, a relative change of -5.5%), indicating that the filter does not introduce additional class imbalance.

7.2. Augmentation and Diversity Preservation. The persistence of the quality advantage after five-fold augmentation has a direct implication for pipeline design. Filtering first produces a cleaner source pool, and augmentation then propagates the statistical properties of that pool into the expanded training set. The observation that Filtered Augmented yields the lowest σ_{SNR} among the four tested configurations (1.71 dB) is consistent with this interpretation and favors the filter-then-augment sequence over the reverse ordering.

The reduction in relative advantage from $+9.2\%$ before augmentation to $+7.7\%$ after augmentation is not unexpected. Augmentation introduces controlled perturbations that compress quality differences across samples. What matters here is that the benefit of filtering remains visible after this compression. This indicates that the separation introduced by the filtering stage is not erased by the augmentation process.

The diversity analysis leads to a similar conclusion. The difference between the two augmented configurations is $\Delta D = 0.008$ on a $[0, 2]$ scale, which is small in magnitude. Although filtering reduces diversity more visibly before augmentation, that gap narrows substantially once the training set is expanded through controlled transformations. From an operational perspective, the results suggest that the quality improvement obtained by filtering is achieved with little effect on the photometric diversity of the final augmented training set.

7.3. SNR Versus SGE and Bootstrap Validation. The opposite responses of SNR and SGE to augmentation provide a useful basis for selecting a quality proxy in augmentation-aware pipelines. A suitable proxy should rank source images above their augmented derivatives, since augmentation deliberately introduces controlled perturbations. SNR follows this expected ordering, whereas SGE does not. For this reason, SNR is the more appropriate choice for pre-augmentation quality filtering in the present setting. The bootstrap analysis complements this interpretation. The paired comparison between Filtered Augmented and Raw Augmented yields $\overline{\Delta}^{\text{SGE}} = -6.4 \times 10^{-5}$, with a 95% confidence interval of $[-0.0077, +0.0076]$ (contains zero) and $P(\Delta > 0) = 0.505$, confirming that pre-filtering does not measurably alter the structural gradient-energy response of images after augmentation. By contrast, the augmentation effect yields a 95% confidence interval of $[+0.112, +0.148]$ (entirely above zero) and $P(\Delta > 0) = 0.825$, showing that the same procedure is sensitive enough to detect structural change when such a change is present. The non-parametric bootstrap framework is appropriate here because it avoids imposing a parametric distribution on the paired SGE differences [21].

7.4. Parameter Design and Transferability. The algorithm relies on three design constants: $\alpha = 3.0$, $k_{\min} = 0.5$, and $k_{\max} = 2.0$. As shown in Section 3.1, these parameters produce monotonic and interpretable threshold behavior across increasing levels of heterogeneity: as σ increases, k increases and τ decreases, while the clipping bounds prevent extreme values at both ends of the operating range.

On the experimental dataset, the observed operating point ($k = 1.12$) lies comfortably within the interval $[0.5, 2.0]$, indicating that the algorithm is functioning within its intended regime rather than being dominated by one of the clipping limits. More importantly, the constants α , k_{\min} , and k_{\max} are defined in relation to the statistical behavior of the SNR distribution rather than to crop-specific image content, device identity, or class labels. This makes the calibration rule potentially transferable to other field-imaging contexts, although broader multi-dataset validation would still be needed to establish that claim empirically.

As summarized in Table 4, the proposed method combines several useful properties: it does not require manual threshold tuning, it does not depend on an external quality reference, it does not alter the image content through corrective transformation, and it adapts its selectivity to the dataset distribution. Together with its $\mathcal{O}(N \cdot M)$ complexity, these properties make it a practical preprocessing option for agricultural computer vision workflows.

7.5. Practical Deployability. The $\mathcal{O}(N \cdot M)$ complexity and the measured runtime of approximately 31 seconds (580 images/s on the present dataset) confirm that the filtering stage adds negligible overhead relative to correction-based preprocessing alternatives. This runtime was measured on a desktop GPU workstation; edge or embedded deployment would require hardware-specific profiling before practical integration. The evaluation draws on six source collections spanning multiple countries, acquisition devices, and field conditions, which reduces the risk that the reported results reflect a single narrowly controlled imaging setting. Generalization to other crop types and imaging contexts remains to be established through independent evaluation on those datasets.

7.6. Future Work. Building on the present results, four directions appear particularly relevant for future work:

1. **End-to-end classification validation.** Train CNN architectures such as EfficientNet [22] and ResNet on Raw and Filtered datasets, then compare accuracy, F1-score, and per-class confusion patterns across all 12 classes. This would test directly whether the improvement in dataset homogeneity translates into downstream classification gains.
2. **Extended multi-dataset evaluation.** Apply the algorithm to additional agricultural image datasets covering different crop species, acquisition conditions, and SNR ranges. Such experiments would help determine how stable the CV-driven calibration remains across broader agricultural domains.
3. **Class-aware retention monitoring.** Develop automated reporting tools for per-class retention rates in order to identify cases where acquisition-dependent rejection may reduce the representation of specific pathological categories. This would support targeted supplementary collection when class imbalance emerges after filtering.
4. **Multi-scale SNR decomposition.** Investigate multi-scale or frequency-domain extensions that separate biological texture from acquisition noise more explicitly. Such an approach may improve the precision of the quality proxy for texture-rich agricultural imagery.

8. Conclusion. This paper presented an adaptive SNR filtering algorithm for quality-aware preprocessing of field-acquired agricultural imagery. The method derives its acceptance threshold from the statistical distribution of the dataset’s own SNR values through the coefficient of variation, and therefore requires no external quality reference, no manual threshold tuning, and no image-level correction. The algorithm was evaluated on a multi-source dataset of 17,976 field-acquired date palm images spanning 12 categories and assembled from six source collections acquired under varied devices and environmental conditions. On this dataset, the method retained 86.5% of images, increased mean SNR by 9.2%, and reduced within-dataset variance by 17.8%. After five-fold augmentation, the quality advantage remained visible, with the filtered augmented configuration preserving a mean-SNR gain of 7.7% relative to the unfiltered augmented baseline and achieving the lowest distributional variance among the four tested configurations ($\sigma_{\text{SNR}} = 1.71$ dB). The paired bootstrap analysis further indicated that the filter-then-augment ordering is structurally neutral with respect to gradient-energy response, with $\overline{\Delta^{\text{SGE}}} = -6.4 \times 10^{-5}$ and a 95% confidence interval containing zero, while the same procedure clearly detected the augmentation effect. In parallel, the diversity analysis showed only a very small difference between the two augmented branches ($\Delta D = 0.008$ on a $[0, 2]$ scale). These results support the use of SNR as an appropriate quality proxy for augmentation-aware preprocessing pipelines. From a practical perspective, the proposed method combines dataset-specific selectivity with low computational cost, operating in $\mathcal{O}(N \cdot M)$ time and achieving a measured throughput of about 580 images/s on the experimental platform. Because the decision rule depends on the statistics of the SNR distribution rather than on crop-specific labels or corrective image transformations, the method appears suitable for other field-imaging settings with similar acquisition variability. Broader evaluation on additional crops and datasets, however, remains necessary before making stronger generalization claims. The most immediate extension of this work is end-to-end classification validation to determine whether the improved dataset homogeneity translates into measurable gains in disease recognition performance. Other relevant directions include multi-dataset evaluation, class-aware retention monitoring, and multi-scale SNR formulations that separate biological texture from acquisition noise more explicitly. While improved dataset homogeneity is expected to benefit downstream classification, end-to-end accuracy, F1-score, and confusion-matrix analyses are reserved for future work (Section 7.6) and fall outside the scope of this data-preprocessing study.

Limitations of the current framework are threefold. First, validation is currently restricted to distributional, structural, and diversity metrics rather than downstream classification performance. Second, generalization to non-agricultural domains or highly controlled imaging settings requires further multi-dataset evaluation. Third, the CV-driven calibration constants ($\alpha, k_{\min}, k_{\max}$) are tuned for the heterogeneity range typical of field-acquired agricultural imagery and may require domain-specific adjustment under markedly different acquisition conditions. Addressing these limitations constitutes the primary direction for future work.

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